

Relationship Between Parental Involvement in Their Child's Learning and Academic Achievement in Secondary School in Anambra State

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between parental involvement in their child's learning and academic achievement in English language and Mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra state, Nigeria. The study was guided by five research questions and two null hypotheses, tested at 0.05 level of significance. The design for the study was correlational research design. The population of the study consisted of all the 4,682 SS2 students in Awka education zone of Anambra state and the sample size for the study was 873 students. Three instruments were used for data collection; namely Parental Involvement in Child Learning Questionnaire (PICLQ) and Students Academic Achievement Scores in English Language and Mathematic in their internal examination. Research questions 1 and 2 were analyzed using aggregate scores while Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient (Pearson r) was used to answer research questions 3 to 9. The t -test of correlation was used to test the six null hypotheses at $P < 0.05$ level of significance. The findings from the study revealed that the type of relationship existing between the parental involvement in their children's learning and their children's achievements in mathematics in secondary schools is not significant and the type of relationship existing between the parental involvement in their children's learning and their children's achievements in English language in secondary schools is not significant. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that Guidance Counsellors and the school administrators should work together to help come up with stimulating and engaging activities in school, bearing in mind the needs of the individual and collective needs of the students as this would help improve their academic achievement.

Key words: Relationship, Parental involvement, Learning, Academic achievement, School

Introduction

In every system, there is always room for improvement in both the system and its outcomes. Educational system is not an exception. This seems to be era of increasing concern about the quality of education in this country. States are becoming more involved in the monitoring and maintenance of academic standards, while communities are becoming increasingly concerned about the cost of education,

and both public and private schools are becoming increasingly concerned about continuing to provide high-quality teaching and other educational services with dwindling resources. Parents, on the other hand, want to know that their children will be adequately prepared to achieve highly academically. However, based on decades of research, it has thus become apparent, that academic achievement of students may not only depend on the quality of schools and the teachers, rather, the extent of parental involvement seems to also have vital role to play in academic achievements of secondary school children.

Academic achievement indicates to which extent a student has achieved aims and goals of an instructional environment at school level. Wentling (2012) posit that academic achievement refers to achievement of individuals' objective to various types of knowledge and skills. However, it has been observed that there is a serious decline in the standard of education in the country (Aremu, 2006). This decline tends to affect the academic achievement of students, especially those in secondary school. The standard of education has remained on steady decline, there by leading to an overall poor academic achievement among students in Nigeria especially in core subjects like Mathematics and English language (Okonkwo, 2012).

Using the recently released May/June 2017 secondary school certificate examination result for example, out of 1,471,151 candidates that sat for the examination and whose results were released, 923,486 candidates, representing 59.22 percent, obtained credits in five subjects, including English Language and Mathematics (West African Examination Council, WAEC, 2017). Although the general performance is an improvement from the examinations pass rate in 2016, which stood at 52.97 percent, however, the downward movement in the performance of Anambra state which went from being in the second position in the preceded year to 6th position in the 2017 May/June examination is a testimony of the fact that all is not well.

This poor academic achievement which seemed to have reflected more in Mathematics and English Language among secondary school students in Anambra State is a worrisome situation which ought not to be allowed to continue. Mathematics as a subject affects all aspects of human life at different levels. Mathematics is seen by society as the foundation of scientific technological knowledge that is vital in social economic development of a nation. It is in realization of the vast applications of mathematics that made Eraikhuemen (2013) to posit that a disciplined and ordered pattern of life can only be achieved through the culture of mathematics. Unfortunately, students' achievement in this important subject over the years has not been encouraging at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels of education in Nigeria. According to the Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2015) Nigeria recorded the worst performance in the 2013 / 2014 academic year in Mathematics in the areas of numbers and Basic algebra. Also in English language. Which is considered as a very important subject in Nigeria? However, the standard of achievements among secondary school students in English language is still in a decline state. A Four-year analysis of students performance in West African School Certificate Examination (WASCE) in English Language and

Mathematics in Anambra state, according to National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2015), showed that their performance has been on decline. The data according to National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) revealed that between the year 2011 and 2014, students' achievement record in English Language ranged between 34.9 and 39.7 percent, while that of Mathematics was between 14.6 and 22.6 percent (see appendix).

Studies have also shown that a continued effort of parental involvement throughout the child's education can improve academic achievement (Driessen, Smit & Slegers, 2005; Fan, 2001; Hong & Ho, 2005). Academic failure of secondary school students in mathematics and English language have been linked with risk behaviours and negative outcomes such as; substance abuse, emotional and behavioural problems associated with parents (Annunziata, Houge, Faw, & Liddle, 2016).

Lee and Bowen (2012), Yan and Lin (2015) posit that parental involvement is related with the academic achievement of students and that parental motivation, attitude, support, and commitment affect students to do well in school. It has also been stated that lower levels of parent education and economic status do not undesirably affect the act of students if parents have high motivation and aspiration for their child's achievement (Ogbu, 2013). On the other hand, though parental involvement is essential for all children, the nature of parental involvement changes according to race/ethnicity, parent education, economic status of parents, and family structure (Schneider & Lee, 2014). Parental involvement in their child's learning, is define as motivated parental attitudes and behaviours intended to influence children's educational well-being. It is a multidimensional and bidirectional construct (Christenson, 2014) that has been shown to have clear links with social and academic outcomes for children. Traditionally parental involvement in their child's learning has been defined as engaging parents in school-based activities and events related to their child's education (Epstein, 2015). In the context of the study, parental involvement in their child's learning is defined as parents monitoring, and assisting their children in educational related activities.

Epstein (2015) identified six areas of parental involvement in their children's academic activities: parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision making, and collaborating with the community. If parents are actively involved in these areas, no doubt it will stimulate children's interest in school and positively influence academic achievement. The cooperation of students with their parents and teachers can be very valuable. A student should be willing to learn, take interest, and participate fully in academic activities before he or she can benefit from school. Sarason (2013) notes that schools are no longer interesting places for most of the students; however, this type of observation may vary from place to place or even from school to school in a particular area. Yet attention should be given to how parental involvement influences school achievement.

For the case of African countries, parental involvement in education has also attracted many scholars in relation to its contribution to students' progress. For example, in Nigeria, Eze (2014) comments

that, parents are the first teacher at home and potential in early literacy skills acquisition of their children. Also Eze insisted that, higher academic progress can be achieved if parents become more conscious and have positive attitude toward learning as well as high performance of students influenced by the level of parental involvement. Parents who perform actively in homework and study programme of their children contribute to their good performance. There are schools Acts that create parents as active partners in schools governance; even though low attendance in parents meetings, lack involvement in fundraising projects and reluctance in paying school fees in public secondary schools are the evidence of low parental involvement (Choudhary, 2013). Parental willingness to be involved in pupils homework is high with expectation of fostering students learning and supplementing teachers efforts yet it is hampered by number of factors.

Equally, parental involvement is assumed to be more mothers' responsibility than fathers' responsibility. Furthermore, little studies have shown that students performed better academically and had more positive school attitudes if they had parents who were aware, knowledgeable and involved in their child's learning (Anthony & Walshaw, 2015). Experiences from schools indicate parents are doing less to fulfil their responsibilities of paying school fees, attending parents-teacher meeting, contacting to school about students' academic progress and attendance. Galabawa (2001) argues that, parents and students are clamouring for quality education for all, especially in democratic education system that requires parents to be informed, participate and influences decision that affecting their children.

Unfortunately, the role of parents in secondary education to some extent is limited and much rested on financing and construction of school buildings which is not fully achieved, on the other hand parents' participation and commitment in their academic progress, such as knowing about their children attendance in school, helping with home works is constrained (Galabawa, 2016). Generally, some parents have little or no involvement in all levels of education. Furthermore, in Nigeria, there has been poor performance in English language and Mathematics among secondary schools students over the years and efforts are always undertaken to address the problem. Among the factors that are associated with the students' poor academic performance are the lack of facilities in schools, lack of teachers, indiscipline, unfavourable home environments and parental involvement, (Mihayo, 2014).

It is possible that, factors like: low family income, low levels of education of the parents, poor involvement of parents and other family members in the students' school activities may affect students' performance in English language and Mathematics (Galabawa, 2016). Although there are many factors that affect students' academic performance, the factors related to parents involvements need to be considered for investigation. Therefore, there is a need to conduct an empirical investigation to determine the relationship between parental involvement in their child's learning and academic achievement in English language and Mathematics among secondary school students in Anambra state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions.

1. What are the distribution scores of parents on their involvement in their child's learning in secondary schools?
2. What are the academic achievement distribution scores of secondary school students in English?
3. What are the academic achievement distribution scores of secondary school students in Mathematics?
4. What is the relationship between parental involvement in child learning and academic achievement of students in English Language?
5. What is the relationship between parental involvement in child learning and academic achievement of students in Mathematics?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 levels of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between parental involvement in children's learning and the academic achievement of secondary school students in English Language.
2. There is no significant relationship between parental involvement in children's learning and academic achievement of secondary school students in Mathematics.

Method

This study employed a correlational survey design. A correlational survey design is a kind of survey design that seeks to establish a relationship between two or more variables as well as indicates the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables (Nworgu, 2015; Walter, 2012). A correlational survey design is considered appropriate for this study because it seeks to find the relationship existing between two variables namely; parental involvement in child's learning and academic achievement among secondary school students. The population of the study consisted of 6,279 SS2 students (Source: Post Primary School Service commission Anambra state, 2017). This comprises of all the SS2 students from all public secondary schools in Awka Educational zone under the management of the State Government. Awka Educational zone has a total number of 63 public secondary schools. The sample size for the study was 873 students. This comprised of all the SS2 students chosen from the selected government owned secondary schools in Awka educational zone. Multistage sampling method was adopted in determining the sample size.

Two instruments were used for data collection; namely Parental Involvement in Child Learning Questionnaire (PICLQ) and Students Academic achievement scores in mathematic in their internal examination. Parental Involvement in Child Learning Questionnaire (PICLQ) was developed by Omeh in 2015. PICLQ consists of 18 items based on a 4-point Scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree, While Students Academic achievement scores in mathematic in their internal examination was

gotten from their termly examination. The Parental Involvement in Child Learning Questionnaire (PICLQ) was validated in Nigeria developed by Omeh in 2015. The other instrument Students Academic achievement scores in mathematics was also validated in Nigeria by the subject teacher because it is a test made test that have table of specification. The instrument has both face and constructs validity. There was no need for further revalidated, therefore, the researcher is adopting the instruments. Parental Involvement in Child Learning Questionnaire (PICLQ) has a reliability of 0.81 which was established by Omeh in 2015 using Cronbach alpha reliability in a pilot test. This study is adopting the Nigeria version whose reliability coefficient of 0.81 that have been determined, there was no need for further reliability estimation.

Results

Table 1: Range of scores on parental involvement in their children learning of secondary school students

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks
18 – 44	61	7.0	Poor Parental involvement
45 – 72	812	93.0	Good Parental involvement

Table 1 reveals that 812(93.0%) of the students with the scores ranging from 45 to 72 reported that their parents have good involvement in their learning, while 61(7.0%) others who scored between 18 and 44 reported that their parents have poor involvement in their learning.

Table 2: Range of academic achievement scores of students in English language

Range of scores	N	%	Remarks
0 – 39	2	0.2	Poor achievement
40 – 49	491	56.3	Fair achievement
50 – 69	359	41.1	Good achievement
70 – 100	21	2.4	Very Good achievement

Table 2 indicates that 360(43.5%) of the students with the scores ranging from 50 to 100 have good achievement in English language, while 491(56.3%) others who scored between 40 and 49 have fair achievement where only 2(0.2%) of the students have poor achievement in English language.

Results

Table 3: Range of academic achievement scores of students in Mathematics

Range of scores	N	%	Remarks
0 – 39	4	0.5	Poor achievement
40 – 49	552	63.2	Fair achievement
50 – 69	286	32.7	Good achievement
70 – 100	31	3.6	Very Good achievement

Table 3 reveals that 317(36.3%) of the students with the scores ranging from 50 to 100 have good achievement in mathematics, while 552(63.2%) others who scored between 40 and 49 have fair achievement where 4(0.5%) of the students have poor achievement in mathematics.

Table 4: Pearson r on parental involvement in their children’s learning and their academic achievement scores in English language

Source of Variation	N	Parental Involvement r	Achievements r	Remark
Parental Involvement	873	1.00	0.05	Negligible Positive Relationship
Achievements	873	0.05	1.00	

In table 4, it was observed that there is negligible positive relationship of 0.05 existing between the parental involvement in their children’s learning and their achievements in English language in secondary schools.

Table 5: Pearson r on parental involvement in their children’s learning and their academic achievement scores in Mathematics

Source of Variation	N	Parental Involvement r	Achievements r	Remark
Parental Involvement	873	1.00	-0.02	Negligible negative Relationship
Achievements	873	0.02	1.00	

Table 5 indicates that there is negligible negative relationship of -0.02 existing between the parental involvement in their children’s learning and their achievements in Mathematics in secondary schools.

Table 6: Significant of Pearson r on the parental involvement in their children’s learning and their achievements in English language using probability value of r

N	cal. r	df	Pvalue	Remark
873	0.05	871	0.119	NS

NS = Not Significant

Table 6 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance and 871df, the calculated r0.05 has Pvalue 0.119 which is greater than the 0.05. Therefore the first null hypothesis is accepted. The type of relationship existing between the parental involvement in their children’s learning and their achievements in English language in secondary schools is not significant.

Table 7: Significant of Pearson r on the parental involvement in their children’s learning and their achievements in mathematics using probability value of r

N	cal. r	df	Pvalue	Remark
873	-0.02	871	0.559	NS

NS = Not Significant

Table 7 reveals that at 0.05 level of significance and 871df, the calculated r-0.02 has Pvalue 0.559 which is greater than the 0.05. Therefore the second null hypothesis is accepted. The type of relationship

existing between the parental involvement in their children's learning and their achievements in mathematics in secondary schools is not significant.

Discussion

The finding of the study revealed that majority of the students reported that their parents have good involvement in their learning. What this means is that most parents are involved in their children learning. This could be an indication that the more intensively parents are involved in their children's learning, the more likely beneficial the achievement effects. This may hold true for all types of parent involvement in children's learning, and possibly for all classes of students as well. The finding is consistent with the findings of Garbacz, Herman, Thompson and Reinke (2017). Garbacz, et al. study found that the more active forms of parent involvement produce greater achievement benefits than the more passive ones. Greater achievement benefits accrue than would be the case with no parent involvement at all. Similarly, considerably greater achievement benefits are noted when parent involvement is active, when parents work with their children at home and when they attend and actively support school activities.

The finding is consistent with the report of Eze (2014). Eze's study noted that parents are the first teacher at home and potential in early literacy skills acquisition of their children. Eze thus asserts that higher academic progress can be achieved if parents become more conscious and have positive attitude toward their children's learning. Moreover, taking a closer look at the research finding, there seems a strong indication that effective forms of parent involvement could include those which engage parents in working directly with their children on learning activities in the home. Programs which involve parents in reading with their children, supporting their work on homework assignments, or tutoring the students using materials and instructions provided by teachers, could show particularly impressive results.

The findings from this study revealed that few of the secondary school students have good achievement in English language and in mathematics in Anambra State Nigeria. This is an indication that more of the students in Anambra State performed poorly in both English language and Mathematics. This finding support the assertion of Mihayo (2014) that in Nigeria, there has been poor performance in English language and Mathematics among secondary school's students over the years despite the efforts undertaken to address the problem. Although the reasons for this finding could be traced to a number of factors that seem to affect student academic achievement in Secondary education level. A great deal of research on the determinants on school achievement has mainly been centered on relative effects of home and school related factors such as family background ; a factor that is important determinant of school outcomes, where a school is seen to have minimal effects. For instance, the finding is consistent with the report of Okolie, Inyiagu, Elom, Ndem and Nwuzo (2014) whose findings have suggested that family background is an important determinant of school outcomes, where school characteristics have minimal effects.

This finding support the claim of Mihayo (2014) that in Nigeria, there has been poor performance in English language and Mathematics among secondary school's students over the years and efforts are always undertaken to address the problem. More so, going by the findings of Galabawa (2016), it is possible that factors like low family income, low levels of education of the parents, poor involvement of parents and other family members in the students' school activities may have affected students' performance in English language and Mathematics.

Another finding of the study showed that there is negligible positive relationship existing between the parental involvement in their children's learning and their achievements in English language in secondary schools. This means that parental involvement have little or no impact on student academic achievement in both English language and Mathematics in secondary schools. This finding is in line with Akanle (2007) whose study observed that the falling academic standards and the influencing factors include the roles being played by the parents. According to Akanle, owing to the present economic situation in the country, many poor parents are forced by circumstances to saddle the young ones with chores like hawking wares, clearing the house and doing other menial jobs around the house before going to school and after school hours. Though, domestic chores like these no doubt help to train the children and make them realize that they can and should contribute their own quota to the general upkeep of the family. However, when parents and guardians burden their children with work excessively, leaving little or no study time for their children and their school work is bound to suffer.

The finding of the study equally revealed that the type of relationship existing between the parental involvement in their children's learning and their achievements in Mathematics in secondary schools is not significant. This goes on to show that a negligible negative relationship existing between the parental involvement in their children's learning and their achievements in Mathematics in secondary schools. This means that parental involvement may not really have contributed much to the students' poor academic achievement in English language and Mathematics in secondary schools. The finding is surprising going by the idea that it contradicted the findings some researcher such as Vukovic and Roberts (2013). Vukovic and Roberts's findings indicated that parents influence children's mathematics achievement by reducing mathematics anxiety, particularly for more difficult kinds of mathematics. Similarly, study conducted by Ford and Harris (2017) also established that other factors in spite of family background can boost academic success among pupils. Studies which examined African parents who maintained positive views about the value of education and who hold high academic expectations have children who often experience higher levels of academic achievement. The reason for these contradicting findings could be attributed to the culture and practices of the areas where these studies were carried out. It could also be attributed to the socio-economic disparity of the study participants which could in one way or the other impact of the academic achievement.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that majorities of students reported that their parents are involved in the learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. Few secondary school students have good achievement in English language and Mathematics at secondary schools in Anambra State, the parental involvement in their male and female children's learning and their achievements in English language in secondary schools is negligible positive relationship in Anambra State. The parental involvement in their male and female children's learning and their achievements in Mathematics in secondary schools is negligible negative relationship Anambra State, and relationship existing between the parental involvement in their male and female children's learning and their achievements in English language and mathematics in secondary schools is not significant in Anambra state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Guidance Counsellors and the school administrators should work together to help come up with stimulating and engaging activities in school, bearing in mind the needs of the individual and collective needs of the students as this would help improve their academic achievement.
2. Further studies should be conducted to determine the factors that contribute more to the students' academic achievement. Such factors when determined should to be implemented by the joint effort of the parents and the school authorities.
3. School-based programs and policies in place that will address the specific factors that contribute to or detract students from academic success, especially in core subjects areas like Mathematics and English language should be researched on and the findings implemented in schools in Anambra State.

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